

Chemical Constituents of *Acacia catechu* Leaves

PRADEEP SHARMA, RAMESHWAR DAYAL and K. S. AYYAR*

Chemistry Division, Forest Research Institute, Dehradun-248 006

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*Acacia catechu*¹ provides the raw material for Katha. Our interest in the compounds of this species prompted us to undertake the chemical examination of its leaves.

Air-dried and pulverised leaves (800 g) were extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), acetone and ethanol successively. Column chromatography of the petroleum ether extract (18 g) over silica gel gave compound A, while the ethanol extract (31 g) gave five compounds, namely, B, C, D, E and F.

Compound A (0.3 g), obtained on elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (95 : 5), was crystallised as white needles, m.p. 156–58° (MeOH); $[\alpha]_D^{26}$ –48.80 (CHCl₃, c 0.1025); acetate m.p. 137–38°; positive Libermann-Burchard test. Based on ir, ¹H, ¹³C nmr and mass spectra, it was characterised as poriferasterol.

Compound B (0.08 g) was eluted with CHCl₃-MeOH (95 : 5) and the solid crystallised as yellow needles, m.p. 316° (MeOH); acetate, m.p. 198°; $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3 250 (OH), 1 670 cm⁻¹ (C=O); $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 372.5, 254.0; + AlCl₃ 457.5, 269.5; + AlCl₃ + HCl 427.5, 264.0; + NaOMe 413.0, 327.0; + NaOAc 384.5, 270.0; + NaOAc + H₃BO₃ 387.0, 258.0 nm. It was characterised as quercetin² (m.m.p., cotlc, superimposable ir spectra).

Compound C (0.18 g) was obtained with CHCl₃-MeOH (90 : 10), as white solid, m.p. 272–74°, $[\alpha]_D^{26}$ –60.12° (pyridine, c 0.233); acetate, m.p. 140°, positive Libermann-Burchard and Molisch tests. Acid hydrolysis gave poriferasterol as aglycone, m.p. 156–58°; acetate, m.p. 138°, and glucose (pc). It was characterised as poriferasterol- β -D-glucoside on the basis of ir, ¹H, ¹³C nmr spectra.

Compound D (0.6 g), eluted with CHCl₃-MeOH (90 : 10), was crystallised as yellow needles, m.p. 254° (MeOH), $[\alpha]_D^{26}$ –162.69 (MeOH, c 0.123); positive Molisch and Shinoda tests; $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3 350 (OH), 1 655 (C=O), 1 600 cm⁻¹ (arom); $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 348.5, 255.5; + AlCl₃ 433.5, 274.5; + AlCl₃ + HCl 397.5, 270.0; + NaOMe 403.5, 271.5; + NaOAc 380.0, 272.5; + NaOAc + H₃BO₃ 376.0, 260.0 nm; ¹H nmr (60 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 3.53–4.33 (5H, m, sugar-H), 5.75 (1H, s, H-1''), 6.36 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-6), 6.58 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-8), 7.01 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-5'), 7.73 (2H, m, H-2', 6'); ¹³C nmr δ (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 177.9 (C-4), 164.4 (C-7), 161.3 (C-5), 157.1 (C-2), 156.5 (C-9), 148.6 (C-4'), 145.2 (C-3'), 133.5 (C-3), 121.8 (C-6'), 121.1 (C-1'), 115.7 (C-2', 5'), 108.0 (C-1''), 104.1 (C-10), 98.9 (C-6), 93.8 (C-8), 86.0 (C-4''), 82.2 (C-2''), 77.1 (C-3''), 60.8 (C-5''). Acid hydrolysis gave quercetin and arabinose (pc). Ir, uv³, ¹³C nmr^{3,4} and ¹H nmr were found to be in agreement with that reported for quercetin-3-O-arabinoturanoside, confirming its identification.

Compound E (0.52 g), obtained by elution with CHCl₃-MeOH (90 : 10), was crystallised as yellow needles, m.p.

182° (MeOH), $[\alpha]_D^{26}$ –179.56° (MeOH, c 0.1003); positive Molisch and Shinoda tests; $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3 350 (OH), 1 655 (C=O) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (arom); $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 348.5, 255.5; + AlCl₃ 430.5, 273.0; + AlCl₃ + HCl 397.0, 270.0; + NaOMe 396.0, 270.0; + NaOAc 366.5, 270.5; + NaOAc + H₃BO₃ 367.0, 260.0 nm; ¹H nmr δ (90 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 0.8 (3H, d, J 5 Hz, rhamnosyl-H), 3.09–3.94 (4H, m, sugar-H), 5.20 (1H, s, H-1''), 5.92 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-6), 6.1 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-8), 6.72 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-5'), 7.13 (2H, m, H-2', 6'); ¹³C nmr δ (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 177.7 (C-4), 164.2 (C-7), 161.3 (C-5), 157.3 (C-2), 156.4 (C-9), 148.4 (C-4'), 145.2 (C-3'), 134.2 (C-3), 121.1 (C-1'), 120.8 (C-6'), 115.7 (C-2'), 115.4 (C-5'), 104.1 (C-10), 101.8 (C-1''), 98.7 (C-6), 93.6 (C-8), 71.2 (C-4''), 70.5 (C-3''), 70.4 (C-2''), 70.0 (C-5''), 17.4 (C-6''). Acid hydrolysis gave quercetin and rhamnose (pc). It was characterised as quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside² by ir, uv³, ¹H nmr and ¹³C nmr⁴ spectra.

Elution with CHCl₃-MeOH (80 : 20) followed by crystallisation from methanol gave compound F (0.48 g) as yellow needles, m.p. 236°; $[\alpha]_D^{26}$ –57.79° (CH₃OH, c 0.0984); positive Molisch and Shinoda tests; $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3 250 (OH), 1 655 (C=O), 1 605 cm⁻¹ (arom); $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 360.0, 256.0; + AlCl₃ 432.0, 273.5; + AlCl₃ + HCl 402.5, 268.0; + NaOMe 410.5, 272.0; + NaOAc 382.5, 274.0; + NaOAc + H₃BO₃ 377.5, 261.0 nm. ¹H nmr δ (90 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 3.26–3.58 (6H, m, sugar-H), 5.18 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, H-1''), 5.93 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-6), 6.13 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-8), 6.67 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-5'), 7.48 (2H, m, H-2', 6'); ¹³C nmr δ (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 177.5 (C-4), 164.1 (C-7), 161.2 (C-5), 156.3 (C-2, 9), 148.4 (C-4'), 144.8 (C-3'), 133.5 (C-3), 121.9 (C-6'), 121.1 (C-1'), 116.0 (C-5'), 115.2 (C-2'), 103.9 (C-10), 101.9 (C-1''), 98.7 (C-6), 93.5 (C-8), 75.8 (C-5''), 73.2 (C-3''), 71.2 (C-2''), 67.9 (C-4''), 60.1 (C-6''). Acid hydrolysis gave quercetin and galactose (pc). Ir, uv³, ¹H nmr and ¹³C nmr⁴ were found to be in agreement with that reported for quercetin-3-O-galactoside⁵, which led to identification.

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